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The Use of Libraries in the Italian Regions in the Period 2019-2022

It decreased by 34.9% on average for the Italian regions

Istat calculates the use of libraries. Use of libraries is calculated as the percentage of people aged 3 years and older who went to the library at least once in the 12 months preceding the interview out of the total number of people aged 3 years and older. The data refers to the period between 2019 and 2022 for the Italian regions and macro-regions.

Ranking of the Italian regions by value of library use in 2022. Trentino Alto Adige is in first place for value of library use with a value of 26.6 units, followed by Valle d'Aosta with a value of 20.8 and from Lombardy with a value of 15.7 units. In the middle of the table are Piedmont with a value of 10.6 units, followed by Marche with a value of 10.4 units and Liguria with a value of 8.3 units. Calabria closes the ranking with a value of 5.2 units, followed by Puglia with 5.1 units and Sicily with a value of 4.4 units.

Ranking of the Italian regions by value of the percentage change in library use between 2019 and 2022. Campania is in first place by value of the percentage change in library use between 2019 and 2022 with a value of -23.4 % going from 7.7 units up to 5.9 units, followed by Trentino Alto Adige with a value equal to -24.9% equal to a variation from an amount of 35.4 units up to 26.6 units and by the Marche with a variation equal to -26.2% equal to a variation from an amount of 14.1 units up to a value of 10.4 units. In the middle of the table are Calabria with a value equal to -35% equivalent to a variation from an amount of 8 units up to a value of 5.2 units, followed by Sicily with -36.2% going from 6.9 units up to 4.4 units and from Valle d'Aosta with a variation of -36.4% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 32.7 units up to a value of 20.8 units. Basilicata closes the ranking with a variation equal to -44.8% equal to a variation from an amount of 10.5 units up to a value of 5.8 units, followed by Umbria with a variation equal to an amount of - 46.3. On average, the value of library use between 2019 and 2022 decreased by -34.9% corresponding to a change from an amount of 15.9 units to a value of 10.3 units.

Ranking of the Italian macro-regions by value of the percentage change in library use between 2019 and 2022. The North-West is in first place by value of the percentage change in library use between 2019 and 2022 with a change equal to an amount of -30.8% going from a value of 19.8 to a value of 13.7. The North follows with a variation equal to an amount of -32.5% equal to a reduction from an amount of 20.6 units to a value of 13.9 units. In third place are the Islands with a variation of -34.1% going from an amount of 9.1 units up to a value of 6 units. The North-East follows with a variation equal to -34.6% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 21.7 units up to a value of 14.2 units. The Center follows with a variation equal to -34.8% corresponding to a variation from a value of 14.1 units up to 9.2 units. Southern Italy is in sixth place with a variation equal to an amount of -34.9% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 8.6 units up to a value of 5.6. The South closes with a variation from an amount of 8.8 units up to a value of 5.7 units or equal to a variation of -35.2%.

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Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. A clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient is presented below. Two clusters are identified:

- Cluster 1: Basilicata, Abruzzo, Molise, Puglia, Campania, Sicily, Calabria, Lazio, Umbria, Liguria, Marche;
- Cluster 2: Lombardy, Emilia Romagna, Valle d'Aosta, Veneto, Trentino Alto Adige, Friuli Venezia Giulia, Piedmont, Tuscany, Sardinia.

Considering the value of the average of the clusters we can see that the value of Cluster 2 is higher than the value of Cluster 1. Cluster 2 is made up almost exclusively of Central-Northern regions with the exception of Sardinia. The regions of Cluster 1 essentially coincide with the southern regions with the exception of Lazio, Liguria and Marche.

Conclusions. The value of library use decreased in all Italian regions and macro-regions between 2019 and 2022. On average, library use decreased by 34.9%. However, it is very likely that the reduction in the value of using libraries is connected to the strengthening of the internet and the digital economy. In fact, it is possible to find books, sources and quotes on the internet that in the past it was only possible to find in libraries. However, the reduction in the use of libraries also derives from the inefficient use and modernization of the Italian library network. In fact, libraries can no longer be considered as places to find book sources. Libraries must be understood as hubs for students and knowledge workers with significant digital investment and the possibility of hosting start-ups operating in the sectors of document management and editorial production with new media. Libraries must therefore become places to host multimedia works with attention also to the metaverse and knowledge production methodologies also through artificial intelligence and big data. It is therefore necessary to finance projects for the creation of 4.0 libraries that can host, through new technologies, works connected to the multiverse aimed at the permanent education of the population, offering not only physical but also digital services in the dimension of "*phygital libraries*".

Declarations

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Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

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Appendix

